

Integrating Nanotechnology in Cancer Treatment: Drug Targeting, Multidrug Resistance (MDR) Mechanisms, Therapeutic Strategies and Future Perspectives

Abirami S.*, Ragul vigneshaa K.

Department of pharmacy practice, Jkkmmrf's annai jkk sampoorani ammal college of pharmacy.

ABSTRACT

Cancer is one of the most devastating classes of human pathologies, presenting the versatile range of hallmark clinical features and leading to millions of deaths each year around the globe. 'Nanotechnology' is a growing therapeutic approach that uses nanoparticles for cancer diagnosis and therapy. The fields of nanoscience and nanotechnology have reached the pharmaceutical industry and created new avenues for better treatment through drug delivery. The purpose of targeting strategies is to deliver nanoparticles and their therapeutic payloads to diseased tissue. Multidrug resistance (MDR) is a condition in which treatment with one medicine develops resistance not only to that drug and other members of its class but also to a number of other unrelated treatments. Numerous investigations have been conducted to overcome multidrug resistance (MDR) by suppressing or evading the multidrug resistance (MDR) mechanism. The compound that would reverse resistance against anticancer drugs are called multidrug resistance (MDR) inhibitors, multidrug resistance (MDR) modulators. Nanoparticles based strategies to overcome multidrug resistance in cancer involve using engineered nanoscale carriers to deliver drug more efficiently into tumor cells while avoiding efflux pumps, improving drug accumulation and enabling targeting, controlled release. These approaches help restore drug sensitivity and enhance the effectiveness of cancer therapy. By enhancing the pharmacokinetics and targeted administration of the drug payloads, combination treatment has been demonstrated to improve tumor control and decrease undesirable side effects. Significant challenges in the treatment and management of cancer were highlighted by the application of several nanomaterials in the field of drug delivery.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, multidrug resistance, drug targeting, overcome strategies, cancer.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a non communicable chronic disease affecting the health of all human societies^(6,3). Cancer is one of the most devastating classes of human pathologies, presenting the versatile range of hallmark clinical features and leading to millions of deaths each year around the globe⁽²⁾. It is a multifaceted and heterogenous group of disease characterized by uncontrolled growth and spread of abnormal cells^(5,4). It arises due to genetic and epigenetic alterations that disrupt the cellular relations and results in the dysfunction of vital genes. This disturbance is affective in regulatory mechanisms of cell division, differentiation and death^(3,5). While cancer cells are autonomous and acquire autonomy over these signals, cellular proliferation, differentiation, and apoptosis are all carefully

regulated by regulatory signals⁽⁷⁾. Cancer develops from healthy cells in the body, When the body requires them, normal cells proliferate; otherwise, they die. Cancer seems to develop when the body's cells divide and multiply out of control⁽⁴⁾. Cancer is caused by both internal factors such as inherited mutations, hormones and immune conditions and environmental / acquired factors such as tobacco, diet, radiation and infectious organisms. The causes of cancer are diverse, complex and only partially understood^(1,4). In men, the highest percentage of cancer types occur in the prostate, lung and bronchus, colon & rectum and urinary bladder respectively. In women cancer prevalence is highest in the breast, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, uterine corpus and thyroid respectively⁽³⁾. 'Nanos' means 'dwarf' in Greek, Compounds with at least one dimension are referred to as nanotechnology^(2,8).

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

'Nanotechnology' is a growing therapeutic approach that uses nanoparticles for cancer diagnosis and therapy⁽¹⁶⁾. The fields of nanoscience and nanotechnology have reached the pharmaceutical industry and created new avenues for better treatment through drug delivery⁽¹⁹⁾. Research on cancer is showing progress in the interdisciplinary field of nanotechnology, which combines biology, engineering, chemistry and medicine⁽¹²⁾. Offering clinically beneficial formulations for improved therapy and patient quality of life is Nanoparticle drug delivery systems (NPDDS) ultimate objective⁽¹⁹⁾. Nanoparticle drug delivery system (NPDDS) can improve cancer treatment by addressing the main obstacle of multidrug resistance and delivering drugs to cancer cells at targeted sites with controlled release⁽¹⁹⁾. Nanoparticles are colloidal particles made of polymers or lipids that range in size from 1 to 1000 nm(1m) . They are composed of macromolecular materials and can be used therapeutically on their own, for instance, as adjuvants in vaccines where the active ingredient (drug) is dissolved, entrapped, encapsulated, or adsorbed or attached ^(20,19). Drug delivery nanoparticles are made of biodegradable and biocompatible polymers derived from natural or synthetic materials⁽⁹⁾.The size and properties of nanoparticles utilised in drug delivery systems for cancer treatment are often determined by the pathophysiology of the tumor ^(10,16). Nanoparticles used in cancer therapy often have certain sizes, shapes, and surface properties since these three factors have a significant impact on the efficiency of nano drug delivery , efficacy and achieve enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect⁽⁸⁾. Nanoparticles are intentionally manufactured and designed systems with sizes ranging from a few nanometers to several hundred nanometers, depending on their intended function. They are measured in nanometres(nm), which are 10^{-9} in size. Typically, the particle size is intentionally designed to allow the nanoparticles to penetrate the leaky cancer endotheliums fenestrations⁽¹⁸⁾. More specifically, the size of the nanoparticles plays a crucial role in controlling the spread of cancer antigens. During circulation, small nanoparticles may escape from the blood stream, whereas large nanoparticles may become stuck in the extracellular matrix(ECM) . On the other hand, medium-sized nanoparticles are persistent in the bloodstream and efficiently reach the

tumor tissues intended location⁽¹⁰⁾.Too small nanoparticles (<6nm) are rapidly eliminated via urine. Nanoparticle targeting techniques have advanced as a result of ongoing efforts to obtain successful drug delivery, even though size-controlled drug formulations and nanoparticles themselves have demonstrated effective tumor targeted delivery⁽²⁶⁾. Effective and targeted drug treatment is made possible by interactions between nanometer-sized nanoparticles and biomolecules both within and on the cell surface⁽¹²⁾. The shape of the nanocarriers may affect fluid dynamics thereby affecting uptake. Spherical nanocarriers appear to be more often used right now⁽¹¹⁾. A variety of materials, including metal particles and polymers, are used in the structure of drug delivery nanoparticles. They can be made in a variety of sizes and shapes depending on the construction⁽¹⁵⁾.The nanocarriers stability and blood distribution may also be impacted by their charge. Prior research demonstrated that positively charged nanoparticles were more successful at targeting tumor vasculature; however, a change to neutral charge upon extravasation facilitated the nanoparticles faster diffusion to tumor tissues ⁽¹¹⁾. Drugs bioavailability and rate of dissolution are known to be enhanced by nanoparticles⁽¹⁹⁾. In the drug delivery system which are dependent on nanocarriers , the nanoparticles have been considered as drug carriers. Nanocarriers alter drug pharmacokinetic parameters, increases efficacy and decreases adverse effects⁽¹⁵⁾. Researchers have concentrated on surface modification in order to increase the effectiveness of chemotherapeutic medications⁽⁴⁵⁾. A key feature of nanocarriers for drug delivery is their ability to precisely target cancer cells⁽¹⁴⁾. Targeting certain tumors and delivering drugs to targeted areas are the main goals of employing nanoparticles as drug carriers⁽¹⁶⁾. Multifunctional nanocarriers may stimulate the anti-tumor immune response and improve treatment results by delivering immunomodulators and chemotherapeutic drugs⁽¹³⁾.

There are three main categories of nanocarriers, each with unique features.

- 1) Organic nanocarriers
- 2) Inorganic nanocarriers
- 3) Hybrid nanocarriers

Organic nanocarriers :

Solid lipid nanocarriers, liposomes, dendrimers, polymeric, micelles and viral nanocarriers are examples of organic nanocarriers. These organic nanocarriers can be utilised with a variety of drugs and binders for delivery since they are highly adaptable, have few side effects, and are effective. Enhanced penetration and endurance allow organic nanocarriers, such as liposomes and micelles, to aggregate at the right place⁽¹⁴⁾.

Inorganic nanocarriers :

The crystallisation of inorganic salts produces inorganic nanoparticles, which are three-dimensional structures made up of connected atoms. The binding atoms are primarily metallic or covalent in nature. These particles are hard and well organised, and the body has minimal effect on them. It is essential to create extremely homogeneous, biocompatible inorganic nanoparticles with optimal functional characteristics⁽³⁶⁾. It is Made from metals (eg. Gold , silver) or metal oxides (eg. Iron oxide) these nanoparticles are often used for imaging and drug delivery⁽¹⁷⁾. Examples of inorganic compounds used for therapeutic applications include platinum (eg : cisplatin, carboplatin, oxaliplatin, etc.,)⁽³⁷⁾.

DRUG TARGETING :

Introducing the idea of 'vectorisation' also known as 'drug targeting', is made possible by the introduction of nanotechnology into the medical field, also known as 'nanomedicine'⁽³¹⁾. In cancer treatment, medications are either taken orally or administered systemically, both of which have the potential to cause major adverse effects by off-target accumulation and damaging healthy organs. Off-target accumulation limits the dose that is provided⁽⁹⁾.

Targeted drug delivery techniques are categorised into two types.

- 1) Passive targeting
- 2) Active targeting

The purpose of these targeting strategies is to deliver nanoparticles and their therapeutic payloads to diseased tissue while minimising nanoparticle buildup in healthy tissues and cells⁽³³⁾.

Passive targeting :

Enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, commonly referred to as 'passive targeting', is the process by which a variety of nanocarriers depend on the physiological features of the tumor to preferentially accumulate drugs. The enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect was initially introduced by Matsumura and Maeda in 1986⁽²⁹⁾. Matsumura and Maeda published two important findings that form the basis of passive nanoparticle targeting, they are :

- i) Spontaneous buildup of given macromolecular drug carriers in a solid tumor with leaky vasculature,
- ii) Lymphatic drainage-induced intratumoral nanoparticle retention. This is the basic concept of enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect⁽³³⁾.

The enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect is accomplished by the small particle size of nanoparticles, which have higher permeability than larger particles such as conventional drugs. Evidence suggests that tumor cell growth promotes neovascularisation and extremely large pores in arteries, resulting in a decrease in tumor cell permeability as compared to normal cells⁽²¹⁾. Because of the pathophysiology of tumor blood vessels, the majority of nanoparticles are likely to accumulate in tumors as a result of enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect. Tumors have a longer compound retention time than normal tissues because they lack a well-defined lymphatic system. These characteristics strengthen the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect^(22,30). The enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect gives very limited tumor selectivity, with a 20-30% increase in delivery over normal organs. The enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect is strongly dependent on the intrinsic tumor biology and in particular

- i) The degree of angiogenesis and lymphangiogenesis,
- ii) The degree of perivascular tumor growth and density of the stromal response,
- iii) Intratumor pressure, the effectiveness of drug delivery will be determined by all of these variables as well as the physiochemical properties of nanocarriers⁽³¹⁾.

Although passive targeting makes it easier for nanoparticles to locate themselves effectively in the tumor interstitium, it is unable to encourage cancer cells to absorb them. Active targeting of nanoparticles to receptors or other surface membrane proteins that are overexpressed on target cells can accomplish the second stage in absorption⁽²⁵⁾. It is not possible to employ the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect to target cancer cells in every tumor due to the varying levels of tumor vascularization and tumor vessel porosity depending on the kind and stage of the tumor⁽²²⁾.

Active targeting :

Nanomedicines can be actively targeted by conjugating them with ligands that can specifically target overexpressed receptors or tumor cells^(21,23). In the event of active targeting, chemotherapeutic drugs are included into nanoparticles that are developed to interact directly with cells that are abnormal⁽²¹⁾. Active targeting ligands on the surface of

nanoparticles enhance their ability to target tumor cells as instead of healthy cells⁽²³⁾. In order to target certain alterations in cancer cell biology that are significantly more uncontrolled than those of the surrounding healthy cells and tissue, a targeting moiety is added to the nanoparticle system. This process is known as active targeting. Through ligand-receptor interactions, the nanoparticles will identify and attach to the target cells. The attached nanoparticles will then be internalised prior to the drug being released within the cell, resulting in less off-drug release than in a system that is passively targeted⁽³²⁾. To facilitate the absorption of carriers into the target tumor cells, the majority of actively targeted nanocarriers can be designed to exploit the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect to enter the neoplasm first, followed by tumor targeting drugs⁽²⁹⁾. Changing the polymeric composition of the carrier is one of the many tactics that have been devised to keep the nanoparticles in the bloodstream. To prevent failure, they are coated with a hydrophilic polymer⁽²⁴⁾. A wide variety of targeting ligands, such as antibodies, antibody fragments, aptamers, peptides, entire proteins, and other receptor ligands, have been used to actively target nanoparticles⁽²⁵⁾. The key advantage in active targeting is that drugs accumulate more in tumours than in other healthy organs, which reduces adverse effects and makes drugs more suited to fight cancer⁽²⁹⁾.

(23)

Figure1: Schematic representation of receptor-mediated active targeting and passive targeting through the EPR effect.

MULTI DRUG RESISTANCE :

Multi drug resistance (MDR) is characterized as a permanent resistance to drugs that are structurally and/or functionally unrelated. The population of tumor cells develops cross-resistance to unrelated medications with distinct modes of action in addition to resistance to the treatments that are first administered⁽²⁸⁾. Pleiotropic drug resistance, often known as multidrug resistance is a condition in which treatment with one medicine develops resistance not only to that drug and other members of its class but also to a number of other unrelated treatments⁽⁴²⁾. Mechanism of Multi drug resistance (MDR) in cancer are

- i) Efflux pump(ABC transporters like P-gp)
- ii) Drug inactivation
- iii) Deoxyribo nucleic acid (DNA) repair
- iv) Apoptosis evasion
- v) Tumor microenvironment (TME) barriers
- vi) Tumor heterogeneity⁽²⁷⁾.

When an anticancer medications effective dose rises to an unmanageable level in clinical practice, multi drug resistance (MDR) becomes a critical issue. Since both intrinsic and acquired multi drug resistance (MDR) are caused by a variety of causes, developing effective treatment modalities requires a thorough understanding of these molecular mechanisms⁽⁴¹⁾. Multi drug resistance (MDR) of tumors is one of the clinically significant reasons for chemotherapy failure. Multi drug resistance (MDR) directly causes tumor recurrence and metastasis, both of which have extraordinarily high fatality rates⁽³⁴⁾. The primary causes of the extremely aggressive tumor growth and metastasis are the poor prognosis and the lack of therapeutic effectiveness of different chemotherapeutic agents due to resistance⁽⁴⁴⁾. Changes in cellular or non-cellular mechanisms may lead to multi drug resistance (MDR). Higher vascular permeability results in non-cellular drug resistance, and the lack of a functional lymphatic system limits tumor cells access to nutrients, oxygen, and medications. Cellular drug resistance can be

categorized as either a classical or non-classical phenotype. Reduced absorption of water-soluble medications and enhanced energy-dependent efflux of hydrophobic medications are features of classical multi drug resistance (MDR), sometimes referred to as transport-based multi drug resistance(MDR). Changes in a particular enzyme system, protein imbalance, apoptosis, and membrane permeability contribute to non-classical multi drug resistance (MDR)⁽⁵⁰⁾. The drug efflux mechanisms involving Adenosine triphosphate binding (ABC) cassette (ABC) membrane transport are now the most extensively researched multi drug resistance (MDR) mechanisms⁽⁴¹⁾. P-glycoprotein (p-gp), an adenosine triphosphate (ATP)-binding cassette protein found in cell membranes, is in charge of regulating the distribution, absorption, and excretion of numerous chemical substances, because of the fact that these proteins shield cells from being killed by large intracellular drug concentrations. Increasing the drugs concentration is sometimes the only way to get beyond the obstacles, which frequently results in systemic toxicity. For this reason, increased drug efflux has been identified as one of the primary mechanisms of chemotherapeutics that are resistant to cancer cells⁽⁴⁶⁾. In cancer, numerous nanoparticle systems have been developed and implemented until now⁽⁴²⁾. Multi drug resistance (MDR) is mostly caused by an excess of ABC transporters. Transporters are essentially made up of two different conserved domains: the transmembrane domain(TMD) and the adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding domain, which is upregulated and also known as the nucleotide binding domain(NBDs) . Based on their major structure and homologous sequence, the 48 human adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding cassette (ABC) genes are currently divided into seven subfamilies: ABCA, ABCB, ABCD, ABCC, ABCE, ABCF, and ABCG⁽⁴⁵⁾. Following the first course of treatment, the adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding cassette (ABC) drug efflux transporters, including p-glycoprotein (Pgp), ABC G2 (also known as breast cancer resistance protein), and multidrug resistance-associated protein (MRP-1), are frequently overexpressed⁽⁴⁸⁾. The overexpression of the plasma membrane p-glycoprotein (Pgp), which has the ability to extrude several positively charged xenobiotics including some anti-cancer medications out of the cell leads to multi drug resistance (MDR). Several tactics,

such as the use of colloidal carriers, have been used to circumvent Pgp-mediated multi drug resistance (MDR) and restore the tumor cells sensitivity to anti-cancer medications⁽³⁵⁾. Different cellular mechanisms, such as increased p-glycoprotein expression and decreased susceptibility to P53-mediated apoptosis, can trigger hypoxia in cancer to cause multi drug resistance (MDR)⁽⁴¹⁾. Drug resistance falls into two categories: Acquired and Intrinsic. Intrinsic resistance is the natural resistance that is present before a chemotherapy medication is administered. Conversely, acquired resistance may arise during anti-cancer treatment. Different cellular and molecular reactions might result in acquired resistance⁽³⁸⁾.

Intrinsic resistance can be caused by

A) Inherited genetic changes that cause the majority of tumor cells to respond less strongly to target medications and chemotherapy,

B) Unresponsive subpopulations, such as cancer stem cells, which can lower the effectiveness of anticancer medications and define tumor diversity,

C) Removal of anticancer medications via intrinsic route activation.

The term ‘acquired resistance’ describes a decrease in the effectiveness of anticancer drugs after repeated doses. Acquired resistance can be induced by

A) Second proto-oncogenic driver gene being activated,

B) Altering medication objectives to lessen awareness ,

C) Adjustments to the tumor microenvironment (TME)⁽⁴⁷⁾.

Unwanted cell mobility and enhanced survival in harsh environments are the outcomes of the acquired multi drug resistance (MDR). Additionally, these migrating tumor cells have the capacity to create a new tissue environment by destroying the extant extracellular matrix⁽⁴⁴⁾. In nanotechnology, creating a unique nano-drug delivery system for the treatment of multi drug resistance (MDR) cancers has become crucial⁽³⁴⁾. Nanomaterials have come into existence as a way to overcome these obstacles and open up new therapy options for multi drug resistance (MDR) cancers in recent years⁽⁴⁵⁾. Nanomedicine research is not only a cutting-edge field, but it is also transforming cancer treatments. The fact that Nanoparticles(NPs) have been widely evolving recently in an effort to overcome multi drug resistance (MDR) is also encouraging⁽⁴²⁾. The concept of co-administration of p-glycoprotein(P-gp) inhibitors and anti-cancer drugs is improved by nanotechnology, which combines them into a single drug carrier for simultaneous delivery into multi drug resistance (MDR) tumor cells⁽⁴⁰⁾.

(41).

Figure 2: Schematic representation of different contributing factors of MDR

STRATEGIES TO OVERCOME MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE(MDR) :

Drug resistance may be prevented by using anti-cancer medications that can evade the adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding cassette (ABC) drug efflux transporters. Numerous investigations have been conducted to overcome multi drug resistance (MDR) by suppressing or evading the multi drug resistance (MDR) mechanism. Administering substances that would not be hazardous in and of itself but would inhibit ABC transporters is another way to overcome resistance to anti-cancer drugs. The compound that would reverse resistance against anticancer drugs are called multi drug resistance (MDR) inhibitors, multi drug resistance (MDR) modulators, multi drug resistance (MDR) reversal agents or chemosensitizers⁽⁵¹⁾. Although the discovery of several adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding cassette (ABC) inhibitors shows promise for treating multi drug resistance (MDR), these modulators have drawbacks, including low bioavailability, lack of specificity, side effects, problems with medication dosage, and interactions with other chemotherapeutic drugs⁽⁴⁵⁾. The goal of multifunctional nanoparticles is to accomplish several goals using a single delivery method. Three factors are addressed by multifunctional nanoparticle delivery systems.

- a) Modify the surface to enable targeted delivery and facilitate absorption.
- b) By avoiding the quick clearance of the reticuloendothelial system (RES), you can increase absorption and prolong circulation.
- c) Loading of certain drugs at greater concentrations, which can overcome multi drug resistance (MDR) and produce therapeutic benefits⁽⁴³⁾.

Despite the various mechanisms of drug resistance in cancer, nanoparticles are always engineered to either promote endocytosis or inhibit or circumvent membrane efflux pumps when identifying multi drug resistance (MDR) tumors⁽³⁹⁾. Achieving a high drug concentration in the plasma is a crucial requirement for overcoming treatment resistance in cancer. To ensure efficient intracellular accumulation, multi drug

resistance (MDR) cancer cells require a high concentration and a lengthy retention period⁽³⁹⁾.

Nanotechnology based strategies :

Chemotherapeutic medicines pharmacokinetic and biodistribution in multidrug-resistant cancer cells have been demonstrated to be improved by multimodal nanoformulations made of materials like gold, iron, or quantum dots functionalised with ABC efflux pump inhibitors and target molecules⁽⁴⁸⁾.

Nanodelivery of apoptosis protein inhibitors (IAPs) :

Inhibitors of apoptosis protein are essential regulators of apoptosis, commonly overexpressed in cancer such as melanoma, lung cancer and pancreatic cancer, where they are responsible for therapeutic resistance and poor diagnosis⁽⁵²⁾. Deregulation of B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2) and nuclear factor Kappa B (NF-KB) often initiates a defective apoptotic pathway. B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2) is a well-studied anti-apoptotic protein that is overexpressed in many malignancies and plays an important role in drug resistance, implying that it could be a target for reversing drug resistance. Accumulating evidence has revealed that co-delivery of B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2) targeting SiRNA and chemotherapeutics using nanoparticles offers an alternative to overcoming treatment resistance in cancer⁽⁵⁵⁾. Inhibitor of Apoptosis Proteins (IAPs) suppress apoptosis by binding to and inhibiting caspases, thereby limiting the activation of the apoptotic cascade and boosting cancer cell survival. Thereby utilizing nanoparticles delivery technologies, it can address these issues by directly targeting cancer cells, lowering systemic toxicity and enhancing drug stability⁽⁵²⁾.

Targeting efflux transporters :

Many investigations have shown that chemotherapeutic-loaded nanoparticles can avoid exposing anticancer drugs to efflux transporters. Nanoparticles enter the cell primarily through endocytosis rather than diffusion, and the drug is released in a perinuclear region within the cell, away from the cell membrane and efflux pump. The efflux transporter lowers intercellular drug concentrations by pumping the drug out of the cell, resulting in

treatment failure. The nanoparticle-based drug delivery technology has the potential to improve drug release control⁽⁵³⁾.

Tumor neovasculature :

Nanoparticle-mediated drug delivery to the tumour neovasculature proved successful in treating p-glycoprotein (p-gp) expressing multi drug resistance (MDR) cancer by targeting Kinase insert domain receptor (KDR) receptors, which are abundant in the tumour vasculature⁽⁵⁴⁾. When compared to a combination of chemotherapy and p-glycoprotein (p-gp) inhibitors, this system had a more potent anti-tumor impact⁽⁵⁴⁾.

Hypoxia targeting :

Another element that leads to Multi drug resistance (MDR) is hypoxia, which is caused by abnormal blood arteries and an increase in the oxygen requirement of cancer cells that are multiplying⁽⁵⁷⁾. Due to rapid tumor development surpassing the

oxygen supply capacity of blood arteries, hypoxia frequently leads in the establishment of a hypoxia zone within the tumour. Nanotechnology offers an efficient way to counteract the inhibitory effects of hypoxia on tumour treatment. By sensing low oxygen levels, hypoxia-sensitive nanocarriers use the tumor microenvironment (TME) to execute targeted medication release or boost therapeutic benefits. Some nanoparticles are intended to breakdown or release active medicines under hypoxia conditions, guaranteeing efficient drug delivery within the tumors hypoxic zone⁽⁴⁴⁾. Hypoxia has been found to mediate the enhanced expression of drug efflux proteins. In this process, hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α) is crucial, and its overexpression has been noted in various human cancers⁽⁵⁷⁾. Targeting hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α) is a therapy strategy for overcoming drug resistance. Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α) inhibitors also offer therapeutic benefit in lowering hypoxia-induced medication resistance⁽⁵⁸⁾.

(47).

Figure 3: HIF-1 α mediates interconnected mechanisms during hypoxia, facilitating chemoresistance in cancer

Nanoparticle-mediated gene modulation to overcome multi drug resistance (MD) :

According to a new study, ceramide can restore the production of the crucial tumour suppressor wild type p53 protein. In this approach, ceramide may be

delivered into cancer cells with p53 missense mutations more successfully using nanoparticles. Since p53 is important for apoptosis, restoring p53 activity or other tumour suppressors is thought to be a possible strategy for overcoming cancer drug resistance⁽⁵⁶⁾.

use of siRNA to combat mdr :

Co-delivery of medications and genes can assist overcome chemoresistance in tumour cells by either inhibiting two or more pathways that aid in tumour cell death or by downregulating the genes producing resistance⁽²⁷⁾.

General pharmacological strategies to overcome multi drug resistance(MDR) in cancer :

Use of inhibitors of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding cassette (ABC) transporters to reverse multi drug resistance (MD) :

This is a significant strategy that is gaining a lot of attention. There are two categories for adenosine triphosphate(ATP) binding cassette (ABC) transporter inhibitors. Certain inhibitors operate as competitive antagonists after being able to transport themselves. The others impact transporter function but are not transferred⁽⁴⁹⁾.

Modification of chemotherapy regimens :

High dose chemotherapy regimens may be administered to cancer patients, and non-cross-resistant chemotherapeutic regimens use the greatest number of active agents at the highest possible doses, assuming that drug-resistant mutations do not confer resistance to all of the agents in the regimen. This strategy is predicated on the idea that high doses of chemotherapy may be able to overcome the tumors resistance to conventional doses of anticancer drugs⁽⁴⁹⁾.

COMBINATIONAL APPROACHES:

Nanomaterials based cancer therapy plays a significant role in enhancing the therapeutic efficacy against cancer by employing a combination of nanoparticles⁽⁶⁰⁾. Unfortunately, a number of solid tumours are resistant to treatment, metastasis to

distant organs, and produce recurrence issues in cancer patients. combinational approaches of Nanodrug particles may be used to increase the therapeutic index by addressing metastasis and therapy resistance⁽⁵⁹⁾. By enhancing the pharmacokinetics and targeted administration of the drug payloads, combination treatment has been demonstrated to improve tumour control and decrease undesirable side effects⁽⁶⁰⁾. Certain cancer types react well to traditional treatments including radiotherapy, surgery, and photodynamic therapy (PDT)⁽⁵⁹⁾. By improving pharmacokinetics parameters like large volume distribution and tumour deposition of the components through enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems (DDS) may represent such disruptive technology for increasing therapeutic efficacy and decreasing systemic toxicity. Lipid polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPNs) are one type of nanoparticle that combines the benefits of liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles into a single delivery system. In particular, the dual component structure of lipid polymer hybrid nanoparticles (LPNs) offers a perfect platform for combinational drug administration, in which various medicines can be loaded to either the polymer core or the lipid shell for the appropriate release kinetics and therapeutic functions⁽⁶⁶⁾. A lot of research is being done on using nanoparticles for combination treatments, using multifunctional moiety to target different cancer hallmarks and using a multiple drug loading approach with these nanoparticles. The combination of the therapeutic and/or diagnostic drugs chosen must complement each other for the treatment of cancer in order to increase the efficiency of nanomedicine⁽⁶¹⁾. The possibility that resistant clonal populations of malignant cells would proliferate by targeting cells with distinct effector channels is reduced when the targeted treatment approaches are combined with the use of nanoparticles as a drug delivery technology. Destroying the tumour vasculature, tumour tissue (or tumour microenvironment), targeting cancer cells specifically using nanoparticles, or combinations of two or more of these approaches have all been used to selectively eliminate tumours⁽⁶⁴⁾. Using specially designed nanoparticles for photo dynamic therapy (PDT) based combined therapy provides a promising platform for codelivery of multiple drugs and (action in different models) and Photosensitiser (PS) with the

benefits of improving drug efficacy, reducing potential toxicity in health issues, and having excellent physicochemical properties. By incorporating the elements of diagnosis, treatment, and imaging, a nanotechnology-based photodynamic therapy (PDT) combination showed promise in preclinical investigations. In this regard, photodynamic treatment (PDT) combined with inorganic nanomaterials (such as metallic and silica nanoparticles) and organic delivery systems (such as hydrogels, liposomes, and polymeric nanomaterials) has shown extremely promising results⁽⁵⁹⁾. Targeted photodynamic therapy (TPDT) uses nanotechnology to formulate photosensitizer agents attached to nanocarriers to achieve specific targeting, controlled drug release, and concentration of the photosensitizer agents in the solid tumour environment. Conventional photodynamic treatment (PDT) is the principle and mechanism of targeted photodynamic therapy (TPDT). In order to produce cytotoxic singlet oxygen, which kills cancer cells, an administered PS (photosensitizer) substance is exposed to light of a certain wavelength. The shortcomings of photodynamic treatment (PDT), such as the photosensitizer agents poor dissolution in aqueous media and their limited concentration at the tumour tissue, gave rise to targeted photodynamic therapy (TPDT). The short-lived cytotoxic singlet oxygen is more effective when the photosensitizer agents connected to nanocarriers are then able to localise within the solid tumors subcellular compartments. The addition of cancer-specific ligands to the nanodrug delivery system further improves the photosensitizer agents tumour selectivity⁽⁶⁵⁾. Generally, Monotherapy often relies on the use of a single medication, which is insufficient to cause tumour reduction. In order to overcome cross-resistance and produce a synergistically increased therapeutic effect without significantly enhancing toxicities, combination treatment appears to be standard procedure in conventional chemotherapy⁽⁶⁰⁾. Many nanoparticle-based chemotherapeutics are now in various stages of clinical (or) preclinical research, although a number already exist on the market. Example, Doxil and Abraxane are two well-known chemotherapeutic nanoparticles that are frequently used as first-line therapies for a variety of cancer types⁽⁶²⁾. Chemotherapeutic drugs have been shown to effectively inhibit cancer cells from proliferating. In

clinical practice, many herapeutical agents therapeutical agents are typically co-administered to achieve a synergistic (or) added effect in order to maximise the efficacy of chemotherapeutic treatments and reduce adverse side effects. There are many methods for loading chemotherapeutic drugs onto nanocarriers. Chemotherapeutic drugs can be encapsulated, loaded onto the surface of nanocarriers, or covalently linked to them, depending on the physicochemical characteristics of the payload and the chemical composition and characteristics of the nanocarrier. The choice of nanocarriers should accord with the chemical characteristics of the therapeutic agents⁽⁶³⁾. By causing synergistic killing and directing nanoparticles to cancer areas to prevent the death of healthy cells, targeted combination therapy also enables a lower dosage of the medications to decrease cytotoxicity while maintaining therapeutic efficacy⁽⁶⁴⁾. For example, liposomal nanocarriers have both hydrophilic and hydrophobic compartments because they can transport medications with varying solubility profiles. Nanocarriers not only serve as transporters but also shield payload from oxidative biodegradation and quick clearance. One of the major factors to take into account while creating combinational chemotherapy to produce a synergistic therapeutic outcome is the drug ratio. Co-delivery of several chemotherapeutic drug combinations employing nanoparticle systems has been studied. When compared to other nanoparticles, some can offer more control over the drug molar ratio. For example, liposomes and polymeric nanoparticles may offer superior ratio-metric drug loading, which is more difficult to obtain in metallic nanoparticles⁽⁶³⁾. Combination chemotherapy increases the likelihood of cancer eradication by using the synergistic action of two or more medicines that target various disease pathways, genes, and cell cycle checkpoints in the cancer process⁽⁶⁰⁾. Therefore, combination therapy is an effective approach to improve the effectiveness of cancer treatment as well as an appropriate and alternative way of therapy⁽⁶⁰⁾.

CURRENT TRENDS AND PERSPECTIVES OF NANO PARTICLES IN CANCER :

Nanotechnology is a broad field that expands exponentially and has tremendous potential for treating cancer⁽⁷³⁾. In the upcoming years, it is

projected that nanocarrier-based drug delivery systems would rise to new heights, significantly enhancing cancer research⁽⁶⁸⁾. A promising new era of cancer therapy has been revealed by nanotechnology. because of its benefits in drug distribution, therapy, detection, simplicity of design, and the qualities of particular nanostructures themselves, the use of nanomaterials in cancer treatment has grown in interest^(67,70). Numerous cancer types are being treated in clinical settings with The primary benefits of using nanomed with using nanotechnology for treatment of cancer. In spite of this, there have been significant developments in this field⁽⁷⁴⁾. Targeting cancer cells with nanoparticles is the major focus of the intense ongoing worldwide research. Nanodrug particles unique characteristics are widely used in cancer treatments for a variety of cancer types⁽⁷⁴⁾. When compared to traditional medications, drug delivery systems based on nanodrug particles provide improved pharmacokinetics, biocompatibility, tumour targeting, and stability. Furthermore, nanodrug particles serve as a good platform for combination treatment, helping overcome multidrug resistance (MDR)⁽⁷⁴⁾. The key advantages of employing nanomedicine in cancer applications are

1) The ability to increase a drug's chemical and physical properties, such as stability, solubility, circulation half-life, and tumour accumulation.

2) Boosts efficacy and reduces toxicity by delivering a specific targeted tissue or cell.

3) Drug transport across several biological barriers, including endothelial and epithelial cells.

4) Drug release can be maintained or increased based on the characteristics of the tumour microenvironment.

5) Enable the combination of imaging and therapeutic substances, as well as the immediate recording of treatment effectiveness.

6) By providing the proper medicine percentage to the target and precisely managing each drugs temporal and geographical exposure quantities, multi-drug collaborative administration can overcome drug resistance and increase efficacy.

7) Under particular circumstances, certain nanoparticles have therapeutic properties (such as iron oxide nanoparticles, gold nanorods, etc)⁽⁶⁷⁾. Nanodrug particle-based drug delivery systems have improved pharmacokinetics, biocompatibility, tumour targeting, and stability when compared to traditional medicines. Furthermore, nanodrug particles serve as a good platform for combination treatment, which aids in the overcoming of multidrug resistance. Additionally, producing immunomodulatory factor-loaded nanodrug particles may improve the efficacy of vaccines for immunotherapy. This is an emerging topic, and it is expected that as proteomics research into the mechanisms of cancer formation and multidrug resistance advances, more nanodrug particle-based therapies will be developed⁽⁷⁰⁾. In recent times, Nano drug particles have gained widespread attention due to their effectiveness as drug carriers, their future potential in biomedicine as targeting systems, their utilisation in bio imaging, and their capacity to permit controlled drug release. Nanocarriers can preserve drugs from degradation, enhance their half-life in the bloodstream, and minimise renal clearance⁽⁷¹⁾. In speculation, a highly sensitive nano-biomolecule is made up of a delivery carrier that has an affinity with specific surface receptor proteins found inside the cellular wall bound to a responsive nanodrug particle. The required active molecule can therefore only be concentrated in the targeted tissue via the carrier. Under normal circumstances, this process of particular drug accumulation within tissues or organs is not feasible. Thus, the creation of these multi-model nanoparticles has enormous promise for the treatment of cancer in the future⁽⁷³⁾. The rational design and current advancements of protein-based nanostructures in the applications of tumour diagnostics and treatment are reflected in protein-based nanomedicine. A substantial amount of work has been into creating different protein nanoparticles that include medicinal biomacromolecules, organic fluorescent dyes and photosensitisers, inorganic nanodots, and chemotherapeutic medicines. Single-molecule protein nano rectorors have been studied in recent years with a goal of creating well-defined tiny crystals with a few nanometres in size using a simple, gentle, and controlled method. These crystals have enormous control over their cell uptake, pharmacokinetic parameters, and tumour penetration

for cancer imaging and treatment. These strategies support several protein nanocarrier and conjugate techniques that are often employed to provide a range of anticancer medications⁽⁷²⁾. Future research in Nanomedicine should aim to improve the nanogel micro gel plan, which specifically focusses on building up extremely specific optics into specific cells. This will be particularly important for the focussing of illness cells, thereby reducing hazy updates into the sound self. In vitro and in vivo research should be anticipated to confirm the use of the delivery systems on individuals⁽⁶⁹⁾.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS:

Significant challenges in the treatment and management of cancer were highlighted by the application of several nanomaterials in the field of drug delivery. The development of efficient cancer nanotherapeutics is still a major challenge, and only a small number of formulations have made it into clinical trials⁽⁷⁵⁾. Toxicity, biodistribution and clearance, biocompatibility, immunogenicity, formulation complexity, cost, inadequate understanding of long-term effects, stability and storage, regulatory challenges, and limited targeting efficiency are the limitations of using nanoparticles in cancer therapy⁽⁷⁹⁾. The biocompatibility and toxicity of nanomaterials in biological systems are largely determined by their physiochemical characteristics. In order to prevent the possible undesirable toxicity of nanocarriers to healthy cells, the synthesis and characterisation of the nanomaterials for drug delivery must be done carefully⁽⁷⁶⁾. The characteristics of nanoparticles and the tumour microenvironment make it difficult for nanomedicine to penetrate tumours. The location and configuration of blood vessels affect the way nanodrug particles penetrate tumours. The increased permeability and retention impact of nanocarriers was linked to blood vessel damage and further linked to blood flow and tumour density⁽⁷⁷⁾. In addition, nanodrug particles release drugs gradually because, tumour cells might not be exposed to quantities high enough to cause cell death. As a result, there is a gap between protecting normal tissue from the medication and getting it to every tumor cell at a therapeutic dose. Initiating local medication release from a nanoparticle in the bloodstream of the tumour, where it can diffuse into

the tissue along its concentration gradient, is one possible option. By doing this, radiance on particle extravasation would be avoided⁽⁷⁸⁾. The standard operation of nanomedicine formulations may be disrupted and rendered ineffective by the interaction of nanocarriers with biomolecules and their tendency to cluster into protein coronas⁽⁷⁵⁾.

CONCLUSION:

Nanoparticle drug delivery systems offer a promising approach for cancer treatment by improving targeted drug delivery, enhancing therapeutic effectiveness, and reducing side effects. Their unique properties allow for precise drug release and better accumulation in tumor sites, addressing key limitations of conventional chemotherapy. Importantly, nanoparticles offer promising strategies to overcome multidrug resistance (MDR) by enabling co-delivery of drugs, bypassing efflux pumps, improving intracellular drug accumulation, and delivering gene- or siRNA-based therapies. Although challenges remain in safety and large-scale production, nanoparticles hold strong potential to make cancer therapy more precise and effective in the future. However, ongoing advancements in smart nanocarriers, personalized nanomedicine and biomimetic nanoparticles highlight a promising future. Overall, nanoparticle-based approaches hold great potential to transform cancer treatment into a more targeted, effective and patient-friendly therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Anand P, Kunnumakara AB. Cancer is a Preventable Disease that Requires Major Lifestyle Changes. *Pharmaceutical Research* 2008 Jul 15;25(9):2097–116.
2. Upadhyay A. Cancer: An unknown territory; rethinking before going ahead. *Genes & Diseases*. 2020 Sep;8(5).
3. Hassanpour SH, Deghani M. Review of cancer from perspective of molecular. *Journal of Cancer Research and Practice*. 2017 Dec;4(4):127–9.
4. Mathur G, Nain S, Sharma PK. Cancer: an overview. *Academic Journal of Cancer Research*. 2015;8(1):01–09. doi:10.5829/idosi.ajcr.2015.8.1.9336.

5. Sharma N kumar. Synthesis and Characterization of Anticancer Compounds, Chapter 2. Basic Principles of Cancer Biology . 2025. p. 11–22.
6. Macedo C, Garcia N, Ziegelmann PK. Net Survival in Survival Analyses for Patients with Cancer: A Scoping Review. *Cancers*. 2022 Jul 6;14(14):3304–4.
7. Mohamed FM, Fatih BN, Qadir AA, Abdalla SH, Mahmood ZH. Cancer Publications in One Year (2022): A Cross-Sectional Study. *Barw Medical Journal*. 2023 May 10 [cited 2024 Jun 12].
8. Yao Y, Zhou Y, Liu L, Xu Y, Chen Q, Wang Y, et al. Nanoparticle-Based Drug Delivery in Cancer Therapy and Its Role in Overcoming Drug Resistance. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences*. 2020 Aug 20;7(193).
9. Rezvantalab S, Drude NI, Moraveji MK, Güvener N, Koons EK, Shi Y, et al. PLGA-Based Nanoparticles in Cancer Treatment. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2018 Nov 2;9.
10. Park W, Heo YJ, Han DK. New opportunities for nanoparticles in cancer immunotherapy. *Biomaterials Research*. 2018 Sep 26;22(1).
11. Tran S, DeGiovanni PJ, Piel B, Rai P. Cancer nanomedicine: a review of recent success in drug delivery. *Clinical and Translational Medicine*. 2017 Dec;6(1).
12. Wael Abu Dayyih, Hailat M, Shahd Albtoush, Eslam Albtoush, Alaa Abu Dayah, Ibrahim Alabbadi, et al. Nanomedicine Advancements in Cancer Therapy: A Scientific Review. *Jordan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* . 2024 Sep 24 [cited 2024 Dec 2];17(3):506–29.
13. Hussein Sabit, Pawlik TM, Radwan F, Abdel-Hakeem M, Shaimaa Abdel-Ghany, Al-Hassan Soliman Wadan, et al. Precision nanomedicine: navigating the tumor microenvironment for enhanced cancer immunotherapy and targeted drug delivery. *Molecular Cancer*. 2025 Jun 3;24(1).
14. Sabit H, Abdel-Hakeem M, Shoala T, Abdel-Ghany S, Abdel-Latif MM, Almulhim J, et al. Nanocarriers: A Reliable Tool for the Delivery of Anticancer Drugs. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Jul 28;14(8):1566.
15. Aghebati - Maleki A, Dolati S, Ahmadi M, Baghbanzhadeh A, Asadi M, Fotouhi A, et al. Nanoparticles and cancer therapy: Perspectives for application of nanoparticles in the treatment of cancers. *Journal of Cellular Physiology*. 2019 Aug 22;235(3):1962 – 72.
16. Abdullahi Tunde Aborode, Ayomide Samson Oluwajoba, Aminat Modupe Ibrahim, Ahmad S, Mehta A, Osasere Jude-Kelly Osayawe, et al. Nanomedicine in Cancer Therapy: Advancing Precision Treatments. *Advances in Biomarker Sciences and Technology* . 2024 Jan 1 [cited 2024 Oct 7];6:105–19.
17. Kale P, Supriya Gandotra, Shukla M. Nanotechnology in medicine: A comprehensive review of its role in modern drug delivery systems. 2024 Nov 15;6(4):108–11.
18. Haley B, Frenkel E. Nanoparticles for drug delivery in cancer treatment. *Urologic Oncology: Seminars and Original Investigations* . 2008 Jan 1;26(1):57–64.
19. Saha RN, Vasanthakumar S, Bende G, Snehalatha M. Nanoparticulate drug delivery systems for cancer chemotherapy. *Molecular Membrane Biology*. 2010 Oct;27(7):215–31.
20. Microcapsules and Nanoparticles in Medicine and Pharmacy . Google Books. 2020 [cited 2025 Dec 9].
21. Suhail Ahmad Mir, Hamid L, Ghulam Nabi Bader, Shoaib A, Rahamathulla M, Alshahrani MY, et al. Role of Nanotechnology in Overcoming the Multidrug Resistance in Cancer Therapy: A Review. *Molecules*. 2022 Oct 5;27(19):6608–8.
22. Yu MK, Park J, Jon S. Targeting Strategies for Multifunctional Nanoparticles in Cancer Imaging and Therapy. *Theranostics*. 2012;2(1):3–44.
23. Tian H, Zhang T, Qin S, Huang Z, Zhou L, Shi J, et al. Enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of nanoparticles for cancer treatment using versatile targeted strategies. *Journal of Hematology & Oncology* . 2022 Sep 12;15(1):1–40.
24. Swain S, Sahu PK, Beg S, Babu SM. Nanoparticles for cancer targeting: current and future directions. *Curr Drug Deliv*. 2016;13(8):1290–1302. doi:10.2174/15672018136661607131211.
25. Bazak R, Hourri M, El Achy S, Kamel S, Refaat T. Cancer active targeting by nanoparticles: a comprehensive review of literature. *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol*. 2015 May;141(5):769–784. doi:10.1007/s00432-014-1767-3. [cited 2025 Dec 23]

26. Yhee JY, Lee S, Kim K. Advances in targeting strategies for nanoparticles in cancer imaging and therapy. *Nanoscale*. 2014;6(22):13383–13390. doi:10.1039/C4NR04334K.
27. Khan MM, Torchilin VP. Recent Trends in Nanomedicine-Based Strategies to Overcome Multidrug Resistance in Tumors. *Cancers*. 2022 Aug 26;14(17):4123.
28. Friberg S, Nyström AM. NANOMEDICINE: will it offer possibilities to overcome multiple drug resistance in cancer? *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*. 2016 Mar 9;14(1).
29. Gong C, Ru G, Wang Y, et al. Nanomedicine to overcome cancer multidrug resistance. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2013; 65(13–14):1921–1937. doi:10.1016/j.addr.2013.09.012.
30. BAZAK R, HOURI M, ACHY SE, HUSSEIN W, REFAAT T. Passive targeting of nanoparticles to cancer: A comprehensive review of the literature. *Molecular and Clinical Oncology*. 2014 Jul 23;2(6):904–8.
31. Attia MF, Anton N, Wallyn J, Omran Z, Vandamme TF. An overview of active and passive targeting strategies to improve the nanocarriers efficiency to tumour sites. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2019 May 3;71(8):1185–98.
32. Clemons TD, Singh R, Sorolla A, Chaudhari N, Hubbard A, Iyer KS. Distinction between active and passive targeting of nanoparticles in drug delivery. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 2018;70(8):1013–1023.
33. Narum SM, Le T, Le DP, Lee JC, Donahue ND, Yang W, Wilhelm S, et al. Passive targeting in nanomedicine: fundamental concepts, body interactions, and clinical potential. In: *Nanoparticles for Biomedical Applications: Fundamental Concepts, Biological Interactions, and Clinical Applications*. Amsterdam: Elsevier; 2020. p. 37–53. [cited 2025 Dec 23].
34. Zhang C, Zhou X, Zhang H, Han X, Li B, Yang R, et al. Recent Progress of Novel Nanotechnology Challenging the Multidrug Resistance of Cancer. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022 Feb 14;13.
35. Pandey P, Shukla P, Pandey AK. A brief review on inorganic nanoparticles. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2014;27(2):233–238.
36. Kim T, Hyeon T. Applications of inorganic nanoparticles as therapeutic agents. *Nanotechnology*. 2013 Dec 11;25(1):012001.
37. Anselmo AC, Mitragotri S. A Review of Clinical Translation of Inorganic Nanoparticles. *The AAPS Journal*. 2015 May 9;17(5):1041–54.
38. Vaidya FU, Chhipa A, Mishra V, Gupta VK, Rawat SG, Kumar A, et al. Molecular and cellular paradigms of multidrug resistance in cancer. *Cancer Reports*. 2020 Oct 13;5(12).
39. Constantinides PP, Wasan KM. Lipid Formulation Strategies for Enhancing Intestinal Transport and Absorption of P-Glycoprotein (P-gp) Substrate Drugs: In vitro/In vivo Case Studies. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2007 Feb;96(2):235–48.
40. Xue X, Liang XJ. Overcoming drug efflux-based multidrug resistance in cancer with nanotechnology. *Chinese Journal of Cancer*. 2012 Feb 1;31(2):100–9.
41. Saraswathy M, Gong S. Different strategies to overcome multidrug resistance in cancer. *Nanomedicine (Lond)*. 2013;8(6):903–919. doi:10.2217/nnm.13.54.
42. Yang J, Zhang H, Chen B. Application of nanoparticles to reverse multi-drug resistance in cancer. *Nanotechnology Reviews*. 2016 Jun 15;5(5):489–96.
43. Dawar S, Singh N, Kanwar RK, Kennedy RL, Veedu RN, Zhou SF, et al. Multifunctional and multitargeted nanoparticles for drug delivery to overcome barriers of drug resistance in human cancers. *Drug Discovery Today*. 2013 Sep 18;18(23-24):1292–300.
44. Duan C, Yu M, Xu J, Li BY, Zhao Y, Ranjith Kumar Kankala. Overcoming Cancer Multi-drug Resistance (MDR): Reasons, mechanisms, nanotherapeutic solutions, and challenges. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2023 Jun 1;162:114643–3.
45. Maimaitijiang A, He D, Li D, Li W, Su Z, Fan Z, et al. Progress in Research of Nanotherapeutics for Overcoming Multidrug Resistance in Cancer. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2024 Winter;25(18):9973.
46. Bukowski K, Kciuk M, Kontek R. Mechanisms of Multidrug Resistance in Cancer Chemotherapy. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2020 May 2;21(9):3233.

47. Emran TB, Shahriar A, Mahmud AR, Rahman T, Abir MH, Siddiquee MohdF - R, et al. Multidrug Resistance in Cancer: Understanding Molecular Mechanisms, Immunoprevention and Therapeutic Approaches. *Frontiers in Oncology*. 2022 Jun 23;12.
48. Yadav P, Ambudkar SV, Rajendra Prasad N. Emerging nanotechnology-based therapeutics to combat multidrug-resistant cancer. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*. 2022 Sep 24;20(1).
49. Dong X, Mumper RJ. Nanomedicinal strategies to treat multidrug-resistant tumors: current progress. *Nanomedicine (Lond)*. 2010;5(4):597–615. doi:10.2217/nmm.10.35. PMID: 20528455. PMCID: PMC2925023. [cited 2025 Dec 23].
50. Choi Y, Yu AM. ABC Transporters in Multidrug Resistance and Pharmacokinetics, and Strategies for Drug Development. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*. 2014 Feb;20(5):793–807.
51. Ozben T. Mechanisms and strategies to overcome multiple drug resistance in cancer. *FEBS Letters*. 2006 Feb 17;580(12):2903–9.
52. Yoo H, Kim Y, Kim J, Cho H, Kim K. Overcoming Cancer Drug Resistance with Nanoparticle Strategies for Key Protein Inhibition. *Molecules*. 2024 Aug 23 [cited 2024 Nov 8];29(17):3994.
53. Yao Y, Zhou Y, Liu L, Xu Y, Chen Q, Wang Y, et al. Nanoparticle-Based Drug Delivery in Cancer Therapy and Its Role in Overcoming Drug Resistance. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* 2020 Aug 20;7(193).
54. Bai F, Lu Z, Yang D, et al. Nanoparticle-mediated drug delivery to tumor neovasculature: strategies and preclinical results. *Biochim Biophys Acta-Rev Cancer*. 2013;1836(3):145–152. doi:10.1016/j.bbcan.2013.01.002.
55. Saad M, Garbuzenko OB, Minko T. Co-delivery of siRNA and an anticancer drug for treatment of multidrug-resistant cancer. *Nanomedicine*. 2008 Dec;3(6): 761–76.
56. Khiste SK, Liu Z, Roy KR, Uddin MB, Hosain SB, Gu X, et al. Ceramide–Rubusoside Nanomicelles, a Potential Therapeutic Approach to Target Cancers Carrying p53 Missense Mutations. *Molecular cancer therapeutics*. 2020 Feb 1;19(2):564–74.
57. Xia S, Yu S, Yuan X. Effects of hypoxia on expression of P-gp and mutltidrug resistance protein in human lung adenocarcinoma A549 cell line. *Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology Medical Sciences = Hua Zhong Ke Ji Da Xue Xue Bao Yi Xue Ying De Wen Ban = Huazhong Keji Daxue Xuebao Yixue Yingdewen Ban*. 2005;25(3):279–81.
58. Rey S, Schito L, Wouters BG, Eliasof S, Kerbel RS. Targeting Hypoxia-Inducible Factors for Antiangiogenic Cancer Therapy. *Trends in Cancer*. 2017 Jul;3(7):529–41.
59. Yang H, Chih Kit Chung, Yu Z, Huis RV, Ferry Ossendorp, Peter ten Dijke, et al. Combinatorial Therapeutic Approaches with Nanomaterial-Based Photodynamic Cancer Therapy. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Jan 4;14(1):120–0.
60. Gurunathan S, Kang MH, Qasim M, Kim JH. Nanoparticle-Mediated Combination Therapy: Two-in-One Approach for Cancer. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2018 Oct 20;19(10):3264.
61. Shrestha B, Tang L, Romero G. Nanoparticles mediated combination therapies for cancer treatment. *Adv Ther (Weinh)*. 2019;2(11):1900076. doi:10.1002/adtp.201900076.
62. Zhao Y, Sun X, Zhang G, Trewyn BG, Slowing II, Lin VSY. Nanotechnology-based combinational drug delivery: an emerging approach for cancer therapy . *J Control Release*. 2012 Oct 10;158(2):230–241. doi:10.1016/j.jconrel.2012.07.020. [cited 2025 Dec 23].
63. Shrestha B, Wang L, Brey EM, Uribe GR, Tang L. Smart Nanoparticles for Chemo-Based Combinational Therapy. *Pharmaceutics*. 2021 Jun 8;13(6):853.
64. Kydd J, Jadia R, Velpurisiva P, Gad A, Paliwal S, Rai P. Targeting Strategies for the Combination Treatment of Cancer Using Drug Delivery Systems. *Pharmaceutics*. 2017 Oct 14;9(4):46.
65. Matlou GG, Abrahamse H. Hybrid Inorganic-Organic Core-Shell Nanodrug Systems in Targeted Photodynamic Therapy of Cancer. *Pharmaceutics [Internet]*. 2021 Oct 23 [cited 2025 Dec 13];13(11):1773.
66. Liu J, Cheng H, Han L, Qiang Z, Zhang X, Gao W, et al. Synergistic combination therapy of lung cancer using paclitaxel- and triptolide-co-loaded lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles. *Drug Design,*

- Development and Therapy. 2018 Sep;Volume 12:3199–209.
67. Pei Z, Chen S, Ding L, Liu J, Cui X, Li F, et al. Current perspectives and trend of nanomedicine in cancer: A review and bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Controlled Release: Official Journal of the Controlled Release Society* [Internet]. 2022 Dec 1;352:211–41.
68. Wang X, Wu C, Liu S, Peng D. Combinatorial therapeutic strategies for enhanced delivery of therapeutics to brain cancer cells through nanocarriers: current trends and future perspectives. *Drug Delivery*. 2022 May 9;29(1):1370–83.
69. Kiran Dudhat, Malay kumar Chotaliya, Rani GI. An Investigation of Current Trends and Future Possibilities for the Use of Nanoparticles in the Treatment of Skin Cancer. *E3S Web of Conferences*. 2025 Jan 1;619:05006–6.
70. Gavas S, Quazi S, Karpiński TM. Nanoparticles for Cancer Therapy: Current Progress and Challenges. *Nanoscale Research Letters*. 2021 Dec;16(1).
71. Bhosale rr, janugade bu, chavan dd, thorat vm. Current perspectives on applications of nanoparticles for cancer management. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2023 Nov 1;1–10.
72. Fan Z, Iqbal H, Ni J, Naveed Ullah Khan, Irshad S, Razzaq A, et al. Rationalized landscape on protein-based cancer nanomedicine: Recent progress and challenges. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics X*. 2024 Mar 1;100238–8.
73. Gonciar D, Mocan T, Matea CT, Zdrehus C, Mosteanu O, Mocan L, et al. Nanotechnology in metastatic cancer treatment: Current Achievements and Future Research Trends. *Journal of Cancer* . 2019 [cited 2020 Jan 7];10(6):1358–69.
74. Deivayanai VC, Thamarai P, Karishma S, Saravanan A, Yaashikaa PR, Vickram AS, et al. A comprehensive review on advances in nanoparticle-mediated cancer therapeutics: Current research and future perspectives. *Cancer Pathogenesis and Therapy*. 2024 Dec;
75. Spencer DM, Puranik AS, Peppas NA. Intelligent nanoparticles for advanced drug delivery in cancer treatment. 2015 Feb 1;7:84–92.
76. Neetika, Sharma M, Thakur P, Gaur P, Rani GM, Rustagi S, et al. Cancer treatment and toxicity outlook of nanoparticles. *Environmental Research* . 2023 Nov 15;237:116870.
77. Munir MU. Nanomedicine Penetration to Tumor: Challenges, and Advanced Strategies to Tackle This Issue. *Cancers*. 2022 Jun 13;14(12):2904.
78. Manzoor AA, Lindner LH, Landon CD, Park JY, Simnick AJ, Dreher MR, et al. Overcoming limitations in nanoparticle drug delivery: triggered, intravascular release to improve drug penetration into tumors. *Cancer Research* . 2012 Nov 1;72(21):5566–75.
79. Ammar MM, Ali R, Abd Elaziz NA, Habib H, Abbas FM, Yassin MT, et al. ssssNanotechnology in oncology: advances in biosynthesis, drug delivery, and theranostics. *Discover Oncology*. 2025 Jun 21;16(1).

HOW TO CITE: Abirami S.*, Ragul vigneshaa K., Integrating Nanotechnology in Cancer Treatment: Drug Targeting, Multidrug Resistance (MDR) Mechanisms, Therapeutic Strategies and Future Perspectives, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (6), 814-829. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20844659>

